

SIGNAL AND IMAGE PROCESSING FOR THERMOGRAPHY NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF AIRCRAFT AND AEROSPACE MATERIALS

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Abstract

Infrared Thermography is commonly used in aircraft production and aerospace in general for the quality assessment and the non-destructive evaluation of materials and structures. Thermography can inspect large areas at once, detecting surface and subsurface defects, operating in non-contact and in reflection mode, i.e. having the access only to one side of the sample. However, there is still large margins of improvement, especially for what concern thermal signal and image processing and post-processing. In the framework of the MSCA-ITN-2016 NDTonAIR project, various aspects of the above are investigated to optimize all the steps of the measurement and analysis processes. Coded excitation signals and pulse-compression are used to increase the signal-to-noise ratio of the measurement while preserving the information content of pulsed-thermography. The virtual wave concept is exploited to enhance the resolution of 3D imaging procedures by compensating diffusion and dispersion of thermal waves. Feature extraction and machine learning algorithms are implemented to improve defect detection and classification. In this work, all these steps are illustrated and the possibility of merging them in a unique procedure is shown.

Keywords

NDT, Active Thermography, Virtual Wave, Pulse-compression, Coded waveform, Kernel Principal Component Analysis, Data fusion.

1.0 Introduction

In the last decades, the need to reduce fuel consumption in air transport, led to an impressive growth of the use of composite parts for manufacturing light weight aircrafts structures [Cantwell 1991, Wang 2011, Miller 2011, Apalowo 2017]. This process, which is still ongoing, represented and represents an engaging challenge for material scientists, for aircraft designers and producers but also for NDT and SHM scientists and technicians. Traditional techniques have been modified and new ones have been developed to cope with the peculiarities of composite structures and for allowing assessing the quality/structural integrity of aircraft parts, both during the manufacturing and in-operation stages. Ultrasonic testing (UT) [Scarponi 2000, Bisle 2006, Castellano 2014], guided waves [Rose 2000, Raišutis 2010, Diamanti2010], and thermography (TH) [Vavilov1993, Avdelidis2003, Meola 2004, Mayr 2014, Cheng 2011, He 2014, Malekmohammadi 2019] are among the most adopted techniques for composites inspection. However, there is still a gap between the composite materials development and the actual nondestructive evaluation (NDE) capabilities that limits an even larger use of composite parts since reliable and/or certified NDT and SHM procedures still miss for many composites' applications in aircraft design. This issue has triggered the development of new sensors, inspection schemes and post-processing techniques, all aimed at shrinking the mentioned disparity. In particular, the unique combination of pros showed by TH, stimulated significant research efforts aimed at developing TH theory and technology. In fact, with respect to other NDT techniques TH can inspect large areas, detecting surface and subsurface defects, operating in non-contact and in reflection mode, giving an easy reading of the results in the form of images.

In the framework of the MSCA-ITN-2016 NDTonAIR project (www.ndtonair.eu), various aspects are under investigation to push at the maximum the TH inspection capability in terms of defect detection and spatial, especially depth, resolution. In particular, signal and image processing techniques are applied in all the steps of the measurement and data processing chain: (i) coded excitation signals and pulse-compression are proposed for increasing the SNR of the measurement while preserving the information content of pulsed-thermography [Silipigni 2017], (ii) the virtual wave (VW) concept is exploited to enhance the resolution of 3D imaging procedures by compensating diffusion and dispersion of thermal waves [Burgholzer 2017, Mayr 2018], (iii) feature extraction and machine learning algorithms are implemented to improve defect detection and classification contextually with the development of automatic analysis procedures [Yi 2019].

In this paper, the afore-mentioned techniques are illustrated and the possibility of merging them in a single procedure is proposed. To this aim, a benchmark Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) sample containing thin Teflon[®] inserts embedded at different depths mimicking delamination was inspected by TH, and the proposed post-processing techniques have been applied to the collected data. The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 includes shorts yet thorough mathematical descriptions of Pulsed-Thermography (PT) Pulse-Compression Thermography (PuCT), VW and the proposed feature extraction methodology. The experimental setups and the CFRP specimen are detailed in Section 3.

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Section 4 shows both the results attained by using each single proposed strategy and the combination of them. The manuscript ends up in Section 5, wherein conclusion and future works are drawn.

2.0 Experimental/Materials and methods

2.1 Pulse Compression Thermography

A commonly-adopted active TH scheme is the so-called PT, which is exploited in a wide range of non-destructive technique applications. In PT, high-power flash head lamps (some kJ of energy) are employed to heat up the SUT surface, and the same surface is usually monitored by the IR camera. The flash induces a change of the surface temperature causing a heat diffusion toward the inner part of the SUT to retrieve thermal equilibrium. A change in the related pixels' temperature decay curves – acquired by means of an infrared camera – can be observed if the heat diffusion is hampered by the presence of an anomaly. From a system-theory perspective, neglecting non-linear phenomena, the cooling curve $h_{j_x, j_y}(t)$ of the (j_x, j_y) pixel can be considered as its thermal 1D impulse response where the flash excitation plays the role of the impulsive Dirac delta excitation $\delta(t)$ – this is of utmost importance as the system behaviour is univocally characterised by the collection of its $h_{j_x, j_y}(t)$. The major drawback in applying PT is that the SNR level is directly related and proportional to the available flash power. In this framework, the use of coded modulated heating stimuli in combination with pulse-compression (PuCT) helps in unlinking the SNR level from the heat source power. In PuCT the heat source emission is modulated by means of a coded waveform, which can be designed to cope with a wanted excitation spectrum. As a result, the energy is delivered to the SUT spread both in time and in frequency, assuring a great flexibility in the measurement procedure and making possible to reach a desired SNR level, though exploiting low power heat source. The reader is referred to the literature on the topic for further details.

The following is the mathematical theory at the base of the PuCT. A coded excitation $s(t)$ is provided along with the so-called matched filter $\Psi(t)$ such that their convolution, here represented by the symbol “*”, approximates the Dirac's Delta function: $s(t) * \Psi(t) \approx \delta(t)$. $s(t)$ excites the SUT that outputs the signal $y(t) = h(t) * s(t)$. By exploiting the properties of linear systems, an estimate of $h(t)$ is retrieved by convolving the system output $y(t)$ with $\Psi(t)$:

$$y(t) * \Psi(t) = (h(t) * s(t)) * \Psi(t) = h(t) * (s(t) * \Psi(t)) \approx h(t) * \delta(t) \approx h(t) = \tilde{h}(t). \quad (1)$$

Many possible choices of the pair $\{s(t), \Psi(t)\}$ were proposed in literature and applied also to PuCT (Barker codes [Silipigni 2017], linear and non-linear chirp signals [Laureti 2018]). In all the cases, $\Psi(t) = s(-t)$ maximizes the SNR. It is worth to highlight two physical aspects that differentiate PuCT from other PuC applications: (i) the difficulty in realizing a bipolar heat source and (ii) the need to distribute, in a reasonable measurement time, the excitation energy in a frequency band wide enough for ensuring contextually both sensitivity to hidden defects and high time-resolution in the $\tilde{h}(t)$. The first issue was successfully tackled in [Silipigni 2017] where it was shown how to optimally apply PuC while using unipolar heat sources. To solve the second point, in the present work a

pseudo-noise (PN) Legendre code was used as $s(t)$ [Ding 1998] and the PuC scheme described in [Silipigni 2017] was adopted.

2.2 Virtual Wave

In photoacoustic and in photo-thermal imaging, a short pulse of electromagnetic radiation – modelled as a $\delta(t)$ - is usually used to illuminate the sample. This shock causes an expansion typically known as "thermo-elastic expansion" and an acoustic wave traveling up to the surface of the sample at the same time, at a speed c very similar to that of sound. After the thermo-elastic expansion is fused, two diffusive processes take place inside the sample: an acoustic and a thermal wave will propagate until the surface of the sample. Eq.(2) shows the heat diffusion equation:

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) T(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t} T_0(r) \delta(t), \quad (2)$$

being $T(\mathbf{r}, t)$ the temperature distribution inside the SUT as a function of space and time, ∇^2 , also known as the Laplace-operator, the second derivative in space and α being the material thermal diffusivity, which is assumed to be homogenous over the whole sample; the source-term defines $T_0(r)$ to be the initial temperature distribution immediately after the short pulse. On the other hand, the propagation of the acoustic wave $p(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is described by Eq.(3):

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) p(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t} p_0(r) \delta(t), \quad (3)$$

with $p_0(r)$ the initial pressure distribution immediately after the short excitation pulse. A "virtual wave" $T_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ can be defined in such a way that the same wave equation is valid with the initial temperature distribution $T_0(r)$ and an arbitrarily chosen c , usually set equal to one.

$$\left(\nabla^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \right) T_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t} T_0(r) \delta(t). \quad (4)$$

Now, θ can be defined as the temperature signal in ω -domain, calculating it by means of Fourier Transform (FT) and its inverse (IFT):

$$\theta(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} T(\mathbf{r}, t) \exp(-i\omega t) dt \rightarrow T(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \theta(\mathbf{r}, \omega) \exp(i\omega t) d\omega \quad (5)$$

Similarly, $\theta_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$ is being defines as the (FT) of the $T_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. Now using the (FT) according to Eq. (5), Eq.(2) results in:

$$(\nabla^2 + \sigma(\omega)^2) \theta_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = -\frac{1}{\alpha} T_0(\mathbf{r}) \quad \text{with } \sigma(\omega)^2 \equiv \frac{i\omega}{\alpha} \quad (6)$$

This ends up in Eq.(7), as described in [Burgholzer 2017], which is the sought relation between the measured temperature signal and the virtual wave signal in x – space. It is a local transformation, as the location r is the same for θ_{virt} and θ , and it is valid in all dimensions:

$$\theta(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = -\frac{c}{\alpha\sigma(\omega)} \theta_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, -i\sigma(\omega)) \quad (7)$$

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Eq. (8) is Transformation back from x – space to the time domain (by means of IFT) results in:

$$T(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} T_{virt}(\mathbf{r}, t')K(t, t')dt',$$

$$\text{with } K(t, t') \equiv \frac{c}{\sqrt{\pi\alpha t}} \exp\left(-\frac{c^2 t'^2}{4\alpha t}\right) \text{ for } t > 0 \quad (8)$$

T_{virt} is pixel-wise r (local transformation). It can be discretized to produce a matrix equation $\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{K} \mathbf{T}_{virt}$. Due to the ill-posed nature of the problem, there is a need for regularization of the kernel. This can be conducted for example with the truncated singular value decomposition (SVD) method, (iterative) Tikhonov regularization [Mayr 2018]. Both mentioned methods have been used here for applying VW on PT and PuCT results.

2.3 Kernel Principal Component Analysis

The proposed thermal pattern enhancement method is based on K-PCA method [Yi 2019]. Compared to the traditional PCA imaging, this method considers the impulse response of each pixel rather than each image in the thermal video as independent variable. Each extracted principal component (PC) is a linear combination of the original impulse response and they form the basis of the respective vector space, arranged in order of decreasing variance. Thus, the first several PCs carry the most information regarding the original data. To gain insight on how K-PCA is applied here for enhancing both PT and PuCT data, the implementation of the enhancement method is mathematically introduced here below. Considering the calculated impulse response \tilde{h} 's retrieved pixelwise by exploiting the procedure described in Eq.(1) being reshaped as:

$$[\tilde{h}_1, \tilde{h}_2, \dots, \tilde{h}_{M-1}, \tilde{h}_M] \quad (9)$$

where M is equal to $N_x \times N_y$ denotes the total number of x and y pixel of the acquired IR thermograms. Thus, the reshaped data can be recognized as a matrix having dimension of $Q \times M$, where Q denotes the number of frames recorded by the IR camera, *i.e.* $T_h \times FPS$. By using the kernel method, the \tilde{h} is projected to kernel space ϕ , thus obtaining the kernel matrix $K(i, j)$ as:

$$K(i, j) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\phi(\tilde{h}_i) - \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \phi(\tilde{h}_j) \right) \left(\phi(\tilde{h}_i) - \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \phi(\tilde{h}_j) \right)^T, \quad (10)$$

where ϕ is Gaussian kernel function, defined as Eq.(11):

$$\phi(\tilde{h}_i^1, \tilde{h}_i^2) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|\tilde{h}_i^1 - \tilde{h}_i^2\|_2^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (11)$$

The kernel matrix $K(i, j)$ of Eq. (3), can be simply named as K . The eigenvector α of K can be obtained as:

$$\lambda_i \alpha_i = K \alpha_i \quad (12)$$

Based on the obtained eigenvectors α_i , the enhanced thermal pattern can be projected as:

$$H_{enhanced} = [\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_T]H_{original}^T \quad (13)$$

where $H_{enhanced}$ contains different extracted thermal patterns and they are used to get the enhanced images of the SUT.

3.0 Experimental Setups and benchmark sample description

3.1 Sample description

The CFRP sample contained twelve plies of carbon fiber fabric with an areal density of 200 g/m². Its lateral dimensions were 240mm×200mm and the thickness was ~2.80mm. The fibers orientations were 0° and 90° and the matrix was an Epoxy Resin RIM 935. The artificial delaminations were realized by inserting square pieces of Teflon tape with lateral dimensions of 20mm×20mm and thickness equal to 75 μm between the plies. Nine artificial defects were inserted at increasing depths: the outer was placed under the 2nd ply at a depth $d \sim 0.46 \text{ mm}$, the inner under the 10th ply at a depth $d \sim 2.3 \text{ mm}$.

3.2 PT Setup

Conventional PT data were collected on the same composite sample by using a pair of high-energy flash lamps with a total energy of 6 kJ (Hensel EH Pro 6000 flash system), placed at ~40 cm from the sample surface. Thermograms were acquired at 100 Hz for 25 seconds by means of a FLIR SC7000 camera, equipped with a 3-5μm InSb sensor with a resolution of 512x640 pixels.

3.3 PuCT Setup

The signal generation/acquisition was managed by means of a National Instrument PCI-6711 Arbitrary Waveform Generation board and by a NI-1433 Camera Link Frame Grabber, both connected to a central PC and managed through a custom Labview virtual instrument. The coded excitation was input into a power amplifier consisting on a TDK Lambda GEN 750W power supply that fed four 50 W LED chips in the visible spectrum placed at ~30 cm from the SUT. The AWG board provided also a clock signal for a Xenics Onca-MWIR-InSb IR camera that acquired the thermograms at 40 FPS.

4.0 Results

Figure 1 shows the results obtained by applying VW and K-PCA to both pulsed-thermography and pulse-compression thermography data collected on the same sample. The heat delivered in the two cases is almost the same even if a precise normalization is not possible due to the different spectral characteristics of the two light sources (flash and LED for PT and PuCT respectively). Images in sub-panels (a) and (d) represent thermal images retrieved at different time instants after the application of VW. The images in subpanels (b)-(c)-(e)-(f) represent the first principal components obtained by applying the K-PCA to the time-sequences of thermal images obtained for PT and PuCT before and after the application of VW. It can be seen that by applying only K-PCA on PT and PuCT data, the deeper defect is barely visible, see panels (b) and (e). This is coherent with what found in [Silipigni 2017], where the same PT data were used to compare the optimized PuCT procedure based on Barker codes.

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Figure 1: Results of the application of virtual wave and K-PCA to both pulsed-thermography and pulse-compression thermography data: (a), (b) and (c) VW, K-PCA and VW + K-PCA respectively applied to PT; (d), (e) and (f) VW, K-PCA and VW + K-PCA applied to PuCT.

On the other hand, by applying only the VW, (a)-(e), the deeper defect becomes more visible, i.e. with a higher SNR. If then K-PCA are applied to the output of the virtual wave analysis, the SNR of the defects, especially the deeper ones, is further increased.

This fact proved that the proposed unique combination is improving the active thermography inspection capability.

Further analysis would be also of interest, even if it cannot be detailed in the present paper: the colour inversion of the defects in the VW images represent the various “reflections” of the thermal waves due to the defects. The shallower is the defects, the closer are the various reflections in time and hence the faster is the swap of colour from white to black and vice-versa for the first defects. Moreover, with VW it becomes more visible that different defects are detected at different times, due to the finite velocity of the heat diffusion in the sample. This aspect can be used to estimate the defects’ depth

5.0 Conclusions

Preliminary results show that pulse-compression thermography, virtual wave and kernel principal component analysis were faithfully combined and applied on a CFRP benchmark sample containing thin Teflon defects mimicking delaminations at different depths from the inspected surface. The proposed and novel combination turned out to be efficient in detecting even the deeper defect, which is barely or not visible at all on both PT and PuCT raw data.

This motivate to further extending the proposed method by implementing a quantitative SNR analysis on time trends and an automatic procedure based on feature extraction to detect the detects and to estimate their depth.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 722134 - NDTonAIR”. The authors thank Dr Matthias Goldhammer from SIEMENS Corporate Division for contributing actively to the pulsed thermography measurements.

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